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Future Circular Collider Innovation Study

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REPORT

RECOMMENDATIONS TO INCREASE THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT OF THE FUTURE CIRCULAR COLLIDER FOR MEMBER STATES

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1. Executive Summary

This document builds on the substantial and sound evidence of the socio-economic benefits of investing in large Research Infrastructures produced in the frame of the FCC study between 2014 and 2024. It harnesses insights from academic research and successful policy implementations to propose a series of targeted and concrete policy recommendations. These are intended for CERN, its Member States and their subnational regions to assure that they can fully capitalise on a future particle collider investment.

This **recommendation report focuses on three key pathways** through which individual participating countries can generate socio-economic benefits and thus increase their returns of investments:

1. **Industry** benefits
2. **Training** benefits
3. **Cultural** benefits

The policy recommendations aim to pursue four distinct objectives:

The first objective is to **increase the sustainability of spreading the benefits of procurement**, by enabling more firms across the various regions to successfully participate in future collider related procurement and to tap into the value chain created by the contracts.

Our recommendations in this pathway can be grouped into four categories:

- (i) **levelling the playing field** so that more firms can participate in the procurement process;
- (ii) **supporting SMEs** as these are the firms that are most likely to face barriers in the procurement process;
- (iii) **embedding more firms in the procurement value chain;**
- (iv) **decarbonising the procurement supply chain** through aggregated power purchase agreements (PPAs).

The second objective is to **foster brain circulation**. CERN is an attractive place for people from across the world to study and work. However, many of these talented individuals end up remaining abroad once their project involvement ends, leading to what is often referred to as a brain drain for their country of origin. How can we ensure that more places benefit from human capital formation in a virtuous process of brain circulation?

Our recommendations can be divided into three groups:

- (i) **understanding the local needs for talent** so that Member States and their regions can better target the repatriation of people;
- (ii) **attracting CERN alumni** through tailored initiatives;
- (iii) and **boosting connectivity** so that sending and receiving regions benefit from the human capital formation.

The third **proposal is to extend the benefits of tourism to more regions**. With new Science Gateway, each year more than 300 000 people visit CERN.¹ However, most of the benefits accrue to Switzerland and France, where CERN is located. How can more regions tap into this potential? One way that we recommend achieving this is to turn CERN into a **gateway for science tourism**.

Finally, the fourth **proposal is to establish a systematic tracking of the socio-economic impact**. While we have extensive evidence that shows the socio-economic benefits of CERN's activities through different pathways, there remains a gap in our understanding of what is needed to increase and sustain these effects. Our recommendations focus on **making data and evaluation an integral part of the FCC project** by setting goals for the desired outcomes, the data collection and the methodological approaches to measure these effects.

This document includes a diagnosis for each objective that offers an economic motivation for the proposed interventions. We present the policy recommendations by introducing the supporting evidence where applicable and identifying knowledge gaps that CERN should address through pilot projects and evaluations. We also provide examples of successful cases for each policy recommendation.

A significant advantage of the proposals presented in this document is their stand-alone nature; they can be implemented individually. Many of them can be implemented independently by CERN Member States and their regions.

2. Overview of Policy Recommendations

1. **Moving to a standard tendering approach**, which includes adopting standardized **keywords and codes** and publishing tendering opportunities in the Supplement to the **Official Journal of the European Union (TED)**, can reduce search costs for firms and increase the opportunities for small and medium enterprises (SMEs).
2. **Establishing dedicated support centres within local business association offices** in regions **having concentrated clusters of firms** active in the Future Circular Collider (FCC) relevant sectors. These centres will offer specialised **support to regional SMEs** aspiring to engage in the procurement process.
3. **Unbundling large contracts to enhance the possibility of SMEs** to participate in the procurement process while making the supply chain more resilient.
4. **Setting aside lower value contracts for SMEs**, if they meet competitiveness criteria for quality and price.
5. Conducting **value chain mapping** for the different technologies required to **understand the spatial distribution of procurement** activities and for regions to understand better the local competitiveness opportunities.
6. **Setting up Local Content Units (LCUs)** as separate bodies or functions to be developed within existing regional development agencies in areas where important CERN suppliers are located. They may also be established and coordinated directly by CERN as a '**local economic impact acceleration unit**'.
7. **Creating alliances between regions** with project-relevant sectors to facilitate interregional collaboration and the sharing of knowledge.
8. CERN, together with its Member States, should **facilitate aggregate power purchase agreements (PPAs)** by acting as an anchor tenant or encouraging the creation of consortia.
9. Regions identified as talent contributors, should **conduct a comprehensive analysis of the type of skills that the region needs** to attract with a special focus on profiling homegrown talent that has left the region to join CERN.
10. Creating and promoting opportunities through **grants and fellowships targeting high-skilled individuals to move to their regions**.
11. Provide **repatriation incentives for individuals who stayed at CERN to return to their home region**.
12. **Engaging with CERN staff and alumni abroad** through knowledge exchange and entrepreneurship programmes, mentorship schemes and awards.
13. **Developing**, together with tourism boards, local governments and other research facilities, **science tour packages** that feature additional scientific attractions across Europe and technology hubs **in combination with other activities**.
14. Establishing a **funding stream for sustained socio-economic impact evaluation and data collection** from the outset of the FCC project.
15. **Operating an Open Data portal** that attracts social scientists to use CERN to continue to evaluate the socio-economic impact of investment in science.

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3. Sustainable Spreading the Benefits of Procurement

3.1. Diagnosis

There is evidence that CERN suppliers are, on average, more innovative and more profitable than others.² However, not all Member States and regions have competitive domestic firms operating in industries relevant for FCC, especially when this involves high-tech orders. This means that procurement benefits tend to accrue to a few selected regions. How can we ensure that more firms, especially smaller ones and in underrepresented areas, are able to tap into this procurement value chain?

Building and operating a large research infrastructure also comes at an environmental cost: in 2023, CERN procurement indirect emissions accounted for 30 percent of its total.³ How can this environmental footprint be reduced while making procurement opportunities more accessible to more firms?

Three challenges need to be addressed to achieve these aims.

First, when it comes to bidding for CERN contracts, **firms may face an issue of capacity**. From access over finance to limited human resources, firms have to overcome several barriers to participate in price inquiries, and this dissuades them from competing or locks them out of this market.⁴ This is especially the case for SMEs. Due to capacity, these firms are unable to provide the full bundle of products and services for large contracts, and for this reason, they might not take part in these bids, preferring smaller contracts that are easier to manage.⁵

In the case of CERN, the **requirements of the procurement process and of the supplies might be higher than in the rest of the market**, making the contract less attractive. Prospective suppliers might have to make ad hoc investments for the bid preparation and submission that are lost in case of failure. Searching for bids can also be costly.⁴ While all types of firms face the same search costs, SMEs tend to bid for smaller contracts, and therefore, the relative size of the search costs tends to be higher for this type of firm. Large firms tend to have specialised staff to identify such opportunities.⁴

Second, there is the **issue of access to information**. There may be a gap in intelligence regarding the local industry landscape. The procurement office and CERN Industry Liaison Officers (ILOs) might not always be fully aware of the specific offerings and capabilities of local firms, particularly smaller ones. Assuring a continuous match of state-of-the-art industrial offers and the evolution of the needs at CERN is a time-consuming activity. This problem is more acute for smaller contracts where the suppliers are directly invited to bid. Similarly, firms might not be aware of the opportunities to collaborate with CERN or as part of consortia.

Third, there is the **issue of coordination**. Few firms in the most advanced regions can meet the requirements for the most technologically demanding contracts. On the one hand, this can foster specialised regional clusters that drive innovation and efficiency. On the other hand, the spatial concentration of these benefits can create tensions between different member states or regions within the same member state. This should be avoided. Synergies between different clusters can be identified that would allow more firms from a larger number of regions to tap into these value chains.⁶

Finally, when it comes to sustainable procurement, **smaller firms might have limited options to access renewable energy at a stable and affordable price**. Accessing

Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs), a type of contract to secure renewable energy at stable prices, is more challenging for SMEs due to their individual lower power demand, poorer credit rating and limited expertise.⁷

Against this background, the policy recommendations on procurement can be broadly divided into four categories:

1. **Levelling the playing field.** These policies aim to remove some of the procurement process barriers that might stop firms, especially SMEs, from applying. These recommendations are suitable for all businesses.
2. **SME-targeted assistance.** These recommendations help specifically smaller firms by addressing the barriers that are specific to them.
3. **Value chain embedding and matchmaking.** These policies focus on developing linkages between more firms and CERN procurement offices and between SMEs and larger firms that work directly with CERN.
4. **Decarbonizing procurement through aggregated PPAs.** This focuses on reducing procurement emissions by facilitating PPAs for suppliers.

3.2. Benefits for Member States and CERN

Encouraging more local firms to participate in procurement offers significant benefits for both Member States and CERN. For Member States, this initiative could stimulate increased involvement of domestic enterprises, particularly SMEs. Embedding more firms into the CERN procurement value chain will provide smaller firms with the opportunity to grow, thereby contributing to a more dynamic and diverse economic landscape.⁸

For CERN, the advantages are equally compelling. Encouraging more firms to apply enhances competition, drives down costs, assures the supply of more advanced technologies and thus optimizes procurement outcomes. Smaller firms tend to be more flexible and responsive to supplying specialised products. The acquisition of better business intelligence can lead to improved matching and increased efficiency in procurement process. Ultimately, fostering the participation of a diverse range of firms could contribute to a more resilient supply chain for CERN's operations. This is becoming increasingly important in the current geopolitical landscape.

More competition and better matching have the potential to lower costs for projects, benefiting both CERN and the Member States providing funding.

Decarbonizing procurement can benefit both CERN and the member states. However, it must be clear that CERN will have to carry the costs if the requirements are above the typical average market requirements.

3.3. Levelling the Playing Field to Encourage More Firms to Apply

1. Moving to a standard tendering approach, which includes adopting standardized keywords and codes and publishing tendering opportunities in the Supplement to the Official Journal of the European Union (TED), can reduce search costs for firms, and increase the opportunities for SMEs.

Target	All firms in all Member States
Leading Actor	CERN

3.3.1. Making the Case

Publishing contracts on existing and widely used e-portals can reduce search costs. This is because e-markets provide timely access to tenders, reduce administrative costs and increase efficiency by standardizing tender procedures.⁴ There is **evidence that increased publicity improves firm participation and reduces the cost of procurement.**⁹ Each year, EU public authorities publish services, supplies, and public works worth about 815 billion euros on TED.¹⁰ Given the size of this market, this would be the first choice to apply for SMEs with limited resources rather than smaller portals like the one operated by CERN.

Furthermore, the current CERN procurement system uses its own keywords and codes for economic activities, different to the more widely used **NACE** – the industry standard classification system used in the European Union – adding another layer of complexity for firms when searching for relevant opportunities. The current situation also hinders efficient analysis of the industrial spillover effects. Moving to the standard NACE classification will permit automating this process and increase the ability of CERN to report on procurement effects and to tailor better the procurement actions to the different industry sectors.

To reduce search costs, CERN should **move to a more standard tendering approach** for the FCC. Publishing tendering opportunities on **TED** will increase the number of firms taking part in CERN procurement process. Utilizing standardized codes could also enhance the efficiency and comparability of economic analyses on the social benefits of procurement.

To assess the impact of this initiative on firm participation, CERN could begin **as soon as possible by publishing a sample of FCC-dedicated contracts on the TED portal before rolling it out on a larger scale.**

Alternatively, a specific joint portal for European Research Infrastructures could be developed, but the resource and coordination needs could be prohibitive if not carried by an organisation that acts across many countries.

3.3.2. Case of Success

CompeteFor (UK)

CompeteFor was initially developed for the London 2012 Olympic and Paralympic Games and is an online portal to publicise contract opportunities for capital buying programmes. Since its creation, it has expanded its remit, becoming one of the major platforms that companies use to bid for large-scale public and private sector buying organizations, such as HS2, Heathrow Airport and Network Rail. It also makes the supply chain more transparent by opening opportunities at every level of a project supply chain. Approximately 75 percent of contracts awarded to *CompeteFor* suppliers have been given to firms declaring themselves as SMEs, with two thirds of the suppliers being located outside London.¹¹

3.4.SME-targeted Assistance

2. Establishing dedicated support centres within local business association offices in regions having concentrated clusters of firms active in FCC relevant sectors. These centres will offer specialised support to regional SMEs aspiring to engage in the procurement process.

Target	All SMEs
Leading Actor	CERN Local Business Associations Local Policymakers

3.4.1. Making the Case

FCC related procurement may have higher requirements than those of conventional contracts that companies typically accept. This might also require ad hoc investment and training for bid preparation and submission, which can be lost in case of failure.⁴ Such a situation stops SMEs sometimes from bidding.

Providing assistance to SMEs can be a way to mitigate the risk.

The academic literature has not yet looked specifically at the impact of targeted assistance for SME participation in procurement. The existing evidence suggests that business advice has, however, a positive effect on firms' performance, and that benefits tend to be larger for smaller firms¹². This is even more the case when support is more "hands-on", indicating that a high level of trust and a strong relationship can be beneficial.¹³ Arguably, local business associations are likely to be most effective in delivering this type of training.

In terms of implementation, given the complexity of FCC contracts, CERN should coordinate this initiative by training local business associations on how to access the procurement opportunities. These will then pass their knowledge on to local businesses. At the same time, member states cooperation is necessary to tailor the support to the local context (for example, to address the barriers that local businesses face) and to maximise SME involvement.

Given the lack of evidence in this area, CERN can play an important role in experimenting and contributing to expanding the evidence on what works. Piloting could begin in regions identified as having a high concentration of firms operating in sectors potentially relevant to FCC before being expanded to other areas, if successful.

3.4.2. Case of Success

Sportelli in Rete (Italy)

In 2000, Italy set up a system of supplier Training Desks (TDs) within business associations to aid SMEs on how to use electronic procurement tools. Central purchasing agency experts train clerks in a network of training desks in the entire country that in turn train local businesses on the use of electronic procurement tools.¹⁴ More than 300 desks are active today across Italy. By 2016, more than 2,250 SMEs were supported through this programme. TDs have become the local reference point for smaller businesses interested in public procurement. In recognition of the success of this initiative, this programme won the European eGovernment Award in 2009.

3.5. Unbundling large contracts

3. Unbundling large contracts to enhance the possibility of SMEs to participate in the procurement process while making the supply chain more resilient.

Target	All SMEs
Leading Actor	CERN

3.5.1. Making the Case

Lot sizes can be one of the main barriers to effectively participate in procurement for SMEs. Unbundling large contracts can increase the probability of SMEs to participate: smaller lots can have lower administrative costs and require smaller initial investments.¹⁵ The evidence suggests that unbundling has a positive effect on SMEs participation, but only increases the probability of SMEs winning small-value contracts.⁵ Arguably, other features of the procurement process and the type of contracts or firms should also be taken into consideration.

There is an evidence gap on the type of unbundling that increases firm participation. CERN could experiment on whether horizontal or vertical integration works best. In the first case, calls are divided into multiple similar orders and technologies.¹⁶ In the second case, the procurement processes are divided into different development and production phases, and firms bid for one of these stages.¹⁶ The latter could enable firms in less advanced regions to tap into the procurement value chain. Consortia could accommodate both types of unbundling.

More generally, the potential benefits of dividing contracts should also always be balanced with the associated risks such as the creation of additional interfaces and unclear responsibilities. If lots are too small, they might open the door to direct awards, reducing transparency.¹⁴ When it comes to developing new products, unbundling contracts would not provide a large enough demand to recover the investment costs, and it might reduce the number of participants.

Consequently, favouring participation in consortia with well-defined structure, organisation and performance requirements is needed to mitigate risks.

3.5.2. Case of Success

XFEL(Germany)

In 2010, the European XFEL split a large contract for 840 superconducting radiofrequency cavities between two suppliers, one in Italy and the other one in Germany, both SMEs at the time. The aim was to develop capacity in the two firms and to reduce the risks for the project.¹⁷ Both companies are now able to produce a large number of radiofrequency systems independently, won subsequent contracts and became both the market leaders for this segment. There was a positive and sustained effect on local employment through the supply chain that is still present today.

3.6.Setting aside contracts for SMEs

4. Setting aside lower value contracts for SMEs that meet competitiveness criteria for quality and price

Target	All SMEs
Leading Actor	CERN

3.6.1. Making the Case

Small firms are at a disadvantage when competing for a contract with larger businesses. Under a set-aside percentage of designated government procurement or total spending for a targeted category of bidders that meet the qualification criteria, conditions can be established to permit SMEs to compete.¹⁵ A way to achieve these targets would be to reserve contracts below a certain threshold for SMEs, as in the case of success discussed below.

The main advantage of this initiative is that it produces visible gains and increases the share of SMEs in the procurement process. There could be concerns in terms of quality, price and delivery time as smaller firms could be less efficient than larger ones for certain contracts. While these concerns should be taken into consideration, the experience suggests that set-aside programmes increase SME participation without having a noticeable impact on the procurement costs, even when more than half of the procurement budget is set aside for smaller businesses.¹⁸

3.6.2. Case of Success

Small businesses set-aside (US)

Set-asides are vital tools that enable small businesses to compete for U.S. federal government contracts, which annually amount to approximately USD 400 billion in purchases. Contracts between USD 3 500 and USD 150 000 are automatically set aside for small businesses if they meet competitiveness criteria for price, quality, and delivery.¹⁴

For contracts above USD 150 000, the set-aside applies if at least two small businesses are competitively suitable, known as the "Rule of Two." Larger contracts necessitate a small business subcontracting plan for inclusivity.¹⁴ The federal government aims for at least 23% of its contracting dollars to go to small businesses, with specific targets for women-owned, disadvantaged, veteran-owned, and HUBZone (Historically underutilized Business Zones) businesses.

3.7.Value Chain Embedding and Matching

5. Value chain mapping for the different technologies required to understand the spatial distribution of procurement activities and for regions to understand better the local competitiveness opportunities.

Target	All regions and firms
Leading Actor	CERN Member States Local Governments

3.7.1. Making the Case

A critical step for governments, national and local, that want to maximise the returns from procurement is to better understand the local competitive advantage through an analysis and mapping of the local strengths.¹⁹ This approach is similar to diagnostic processes that underpins Smart Specialization Strategies funded by the European Commission in virtually all EU Member States. In recent years there have been attempts across Europe to map the local comparative advantage, such as the European Cluster Collaboration Platform.²⁰ This is especially important for smaller contracts that are not published on the CERN portal. Often, these mapping exercises reveal that local assets are not contained by administrative boundaries, suggesting the need for coordination across neighbouring jurisdictions. Mapping is not only useful for regions but can also provide valuable insights for the CERN ILOs about a country's or region's industry landscape and assets. This new knowledge would help ILOs facilitate a better matching between a country or region's strengths and procurement opportunities, with the product quality being the priority in this process.

3.7.2. Cases of Success

Emilia-Romagna's value chain mapping (Italy)

In 2015 the region of Emilia-Romagna in Italy mapped the knowledge and competencies available, allowing the identification of 27 GVCs in five primary sectors.¹⁹ The region could then pursue its activities more effectively. The mapping exercise allowed all regional actors of the GVCs to meet and interact, define common goals, and perform critical work towards reshaping GVCs. Emilia-Romagna strengthened its territorial identity, building a globally acknowledged local advantage.¹⁹

Biomedical and biopharma value chain in the Greater Southeast of England (UK)

Prior to the financial crisis, the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission conducted an analysis of the biomedical and biopharma value chain in the Greater Southeast, which comprises Inner and Outer London and three surrounding regions – East, South and South East of England.²¹ Using a detailed mapping methodology, the study identified core industry boundaries, built a comprehensive dataset of firms and categorised them into strategic value chain group. It highlighted the region's specialization in R&D and manufacturing. For this exercise, the use of firm-level data was crucial to accurately map the local capabilities and understand the relationships within the value chain. Having detailed data can facilitate matchmaking, allowing firms to identify potential partners with complementary capabilities.²¹

3.8.Setting up Local Content Units

6. Setting up Local Content Units (LCUs) as separate bodies or functions to be developed within existing regional development agencies in areas where important CERN suppliers are located. They may also be established and coordinated directly by CERN as a ‘local economic impact acceleration unit’.

Target	All regions and firms
Leading Actor	CERN Member States Local Governments

3.8.1. Making the Case

Mapping alone is not sufficient for regions to capture the value of procurement and its spillovers. To develop efficient linkages between CERN and firms and between large suppliers and SMEs, it is useful to set up local content units (LCUs). LCUs are bodies set up within or alongside investment promotion departments that enable new connections between investors (FDI) and suppliers (SME/MNE local linkages).¹⁹ These can take the additional tasks of making new connections between procurement agencies and suppliers. LCUs are described as matchmaking services. They ensure opportune regional GVC embedding and try to integrate local companies into their procurement supply chains.¹⁹ LCUs may also be established and coordinated directly by CERN as a ‘local economic impact acceleration unit’. This initiative can be first tried in regions where large CERN suppliers are known to be located. After evaluation, it can then be scaled up to include additional regions.

3.8.2. Cases of Success

National Linkages Programme (Ireland)

The Irish National Linkages Programme has two key components.¹⁹ One works on accounting for firm differences, and the other on SME upgrading. By targeting both MNEs and local firms, the programme found links and helped build capacity. This targeting process also looked at SMEs and their ability to improve or upgrade their capabilities.¹⁹ The successful programme has now evolved into a more comprehensive initiative working on incorporating Irish companies into GVCs.

Local Industry Upgrading Programme (Singapore)

Singapore uses a Local Industry Upgrading Programme. Upgrading occurs through the training of local firms, perhaps uniquely, this responsibility fell to the MNE.¹⁹ The MNE would second an employee to the local SME, allowing direct knowledge transfer, and in return, the Upgrading Programme paid the employee’s salary - a leasing of staff.¹⁹

3.9.Creating alliances between regions

7. Creating alliances between regions with project-relevant sectors to facilitate interregional collaboration and the sharing of knowledge.

Target	All regions and firms
Leading Actor	CERN Member States Local Governments

3.9.1. Making the Case

The spatial concentration of the procurement contracts and their wider benefits might create tensions between the interests of different countries and regions within the same country. However, while regions compete, the literature indicates that the process of production fragmentation leads to value chains that create interregional dependencies.²² Coordination and cooperation between different regions with a high concentration of firms operating in FCC-relevant sectors and CERN can help address these challenges and enable more firms and places to tap into the value chain by identifying synergies that might lead to better outcomes unachievable on their own. For example, this could enable resource pooling and knowledge sharing.

3.9.2. Case of Success

The Vanguard Initiative (Europe)

Vanguard is a network of 40 industrialized regions established in 2013 with the aim of delivering jobs and growth through industry-led interregional cooperation, co-creation and co-investment. The initiative supports matchmaking and collaboration between businesses across several innovative sectors.²³ It has recently launched Vinnovate, an innovative interregional funding instrument to support interregional collaborative projects for the development of European value chains.²⁴

3.10. Facilitate aggregate power purchase agreements

8. CERN, together with its Member States, should facilitate aggregate power purchase agreements (PPAs) by acting as an anchor tenant or encouraging the creation of consortia.

Target	All regions and firms
Leading Actor	CERN Member States Regional and Local Governments

3.10.1. Making the Case

Adopting measures to reduce procurement-related emissions is a priority for CERN.³ One avenue is that of PPAs. This allows buyers to purchase volumes of electricity from renewable sources at fixed or floor prices for long time periods, typically in the order of 15 years.⁷ Such agreements provide developers the opportunity to raise funds for new renewable energy projects without relying on government support.²⁵

Large corporations have mainly driven the demand for PPAs. This is because SMEs, due to the lower demand, poorer credit rating and lack of expertise, find it more challenging or even impossible to enter a PPA.⁷ Aggregate PPAs can be a solution to this issue. In numerous instances where aggregate PPAs are successful, a lead company organises a consortium of its suppliers to create the necessary purchasing volume.⁷ This could allow CERN's smaller suppliers or subcontractors to procure long-term renewable energy at a stable price and lower emissions across the procurement supply chain. This initiative could also reduce procurement costs in the long term by mitigating market and contractual risks for its suppliers.

There are two potential deal structures that CERN could consider. In the first one, CERN could act as an anchor tenant in a multi-tiered approach with buyers of different sizes and leverage its scale and influence during PPA negotiations to get favourable conditions for its smaller suppliers.⁷ In the second instance, suppliers could bundle together the energy demand without necessarily the need for CERN to act as an anchor tenant. In this second case, CERN would need to require such a structure in the frame of its procurement process.⁷

Although renewable energy procurement associations are successful throughout Europe, the approach is today still an emerging area when it comes to managing procurement actions. It remains to be explored what works best in terms of feasibility, types of suppliers, environmental impact, and efficiency. After conducting a feasibility study on the possible arrangements and type of delivery, conditions and contract duration, CERN could pilot different schemes, potentially with other partners, before scaling up.

From an economic perspective the actual delivery of the electricity by wire is of secondary interest, since electrons are fungible, i.e. interchangeable. Any purchased renewable energy, even if delivered at a different time of use, is avoiding CO2 emissions and is properly accounted in the organisation's environmental impact balance. The approach also serves hedging against volatile electricity prices.

3.10.2.Cases of Success

City of Melbourne (Australia)

In November 2017, the City of Melbourne, Australia, led the establishment of the Melbourne Renewable Energy Project, a collaborative PPA that facilitated the construction of the 80 MW (264 GWh per year) Crowlands Wind Farm in Western Victoria in 2018.²⁶ 88 GWh of the total capacity concerned a PPA, which was signed by 14 public and private entities, including universities, banks, and local councils.²⁶ In 2019, Melbourne became the first Australian city to power all its council-owned buildings and infrastructure solely with renewable energy from Crowlands.²⁶

Pan European Consortium for Future Wind Farm

Three large companies, Royal Philips, Heineken, Nobian, and Signify, have created a consortium to sign a Pan-European green energy deal, securing additional renewable electricity for Europe. The consortium is financing the construction of 35 wind turbines in Mutkalampi, Finland, set to complete in 2023.²⁷ A virtual Power Purchase Agreement (PPA) will provide 330 GWh annually, enough to power 40 000 households and prevent over 230 000 tons of CO₂ emissions each year. Through this consortium, Heineken will source renewable electricity for an additional 31 of its European brewery operations; Nobian will continue its progress in reducing CO₂ emissions by 25% by 2025; Philips will secure renewable electricity supply to power its European operations for a 10-year period and Signify will solidify its leading position on 100% renewable electricity use.²⁷

Energiegemeinschaften (Austria)

The county of Lower Austria in Austria has established a dedicated support for "energy communities" that permit groups of individuals and entire municipalities to procure renewable energy and to invest in the creation of renewable energy sources for the benefit of satisfying their energy needs.²⁸ Support ranges from administrative and contractual matters to financial consultancy.

The evidence for the societal, ecological and financial gains is striking, leading to local renewable energy creation, to more stable energy supply, planning stability and sustained lower energy costs.²⁸

The concept is currently being rolled out in the entire country of Austria.²⁹ Besides contract standardisation the implementation at larger scale also eases the process of obtaining loans and supports. Energy costs are typically reduced with respect to the conventional tariffs, ecological and local industrial growth benefits exist. A full evaluation carried out by the Technical University Vienna has been published in March 2024.³⁰

4. Human Capital Formation and Brain Circulation

4.1. Diagnosis

CERN is an attractive place to study and work, drawing graduate and doctoral students, postdoctoral fellows, engineers and scientists from across the globe. Between 1993 and 2025, the Early Career Researchers (ECRs) intake for the Large Hadron Collider experiments amounted to almost 37 000 individuals.³¹ For them, the opportunity to spend a period in such a stimulating environment means developing experience with new technologies, acquiring new skills and building sustained networks.³¹ This equips them with skills that are in demand in most workplaces, and this is reflected in their lifetime salary premium.

However, a significant amount of these individuals tends to remain in Switzerland and only a few selected other countries after their stay at CERN, contributing to a phenomenon of brain drain to the detriment of their home regions. **How can we ensure that more regions, especially the sending ones, benefit from CERN's human capital formation?** The first step to address this challenge is to draw on the highly skilled workforce migration literature to understand why these individuals first leave, as these might be the very same reasons why they do not return.

When it comes to the migration of highly skilled workers and students, **pull factors play an important role.**³² People are be enticed by **higher wages** and **improved career opportunities** outside their home regions. For ECRs, the **quality of universities and research facilities** and the **freedom to perform research** are key drivers.

Economic factors might not be the only drivers. The extent to which individuals are embedded in social networks can play an important role in their location decisions. For example, if individuals are not successful in creating connections during their stay outside their regions, they are more likely to return.³² Similarly, pre-existing **networks in the home regions increase the probability of returning.**³²

However, the migration of highly skilled workers is not necessarily a linear process or a one-off decision. Instead, it can be better conceptualised as a process of network building across regions, in which **migration can lead to departure and return as a circular process, often referred to as brain circulation.**³² Highly skilled people can move multiple times throughout their careers. **Migration is not necessarily negative for the sending regions as these individuals, by maintaining ties with their domestic peers, can contribute to knowledge flows between distant regions.**³² The embeddedness of these individuals into social networks in the home region seems to be important in brain circulation. This more nuanced view would suggest that efforts should not just focus on incentivising high-skilled workers to return but also on boosting connectivity.

Against this background, our recommendations focus on three areas:

- **Understanding the local needs for talent.** This could enable regions to target the right set of skilled workers for the local economy.
- **Attracting highly skilled talent.** These initiatives focus on incentivising skilled workers to move to different regional or national knowledge hubs. These policies could promote a more spatially even spread of talent.
- **Engaging with the diaspora.** These policies focus on building social ties with workers who previously migrated.

4.2. Benefits for Sending and Receiving Regions

Reversing the brain drain can have obvious benefits for sending regions: as high-skilled workers return, they bring new skills, knowledge, and perspectives gained abroad, enriching the local talent pool. This transfer of knowledge stimulates economic development and fosters innovation and technological advancements at home. Moreover, when these individuals return, they often maintain their professional and social connections with the places they have left.

Even when they do not return, or they return temporarily, there can be benefits for both the receiving and sending regions. When these individuals are embedded in the social networks in their home region, they can contribute to collaboration and exchanges between distant regions, cementing cross-border ties and enhancing knowledge networks. Consequently, both the sending and receiving regions benefit from these collaborative opportunities that brain circulation can create.

4.3. Conduct a comprehensive analysis of regionally needed skills

9. Regions identified as talent contributors, should conduct a comprehensive analysis of the type of skills that the region needs to attract with a special focus on profiling homegrown talent that has left the region to join CERN.

Target	Sending Member States
Leading Actor	Sending Member States and talent contributing regions CERN

4.3.1. Making the Case

Any effective policy **begins with a good knowledge base**. This means a good understanding of the brain drain phenomenon, its characteristics, and its impact on local economic development.³³ The first step is to **understand the regional talent needs and identify mismatches of skills between supply and demand**, with a specific focus on the strategic sectors, for example, those identified through their Smart Specialisation Strategies.

The second step is to **profile the talent that the region wants to attract** or retain and the homegrown talent that left, with a special focus, in our case, on highly skilled workers who joined institutions like CERN. Platforms like LinkedIn have made this intelligence gathering easier than in the past. This information will enable regions to target the individuals that the labour market needs with tailored opportunities.

While there might be benefits for regions in gaining a better understanding of local skills needs, it seems more efficient for this policy to target regions that are CERN talent contributors. These can be identified by analysing data on the regions of origin of CERN current and former staff.

4.3.2. Case of Success

Brain Back Umbria (Italy)

The goal of Brain Back Umbria was to reverse the brain drain trend in the region. The project began by collecting data on labour migration indicators from the Register of Italian Residents Abroad.³³ This information was complemented by a survey sent to citizens abroad distributed using social media. Thanks to this data collection, it was possible to develop a profile of the typical Umbrian resident working abroad, allowing the regional authority to create a database of regional citizens abroad and of a Brain Back Umbria community on LinkedIn.³³ Using this new information, the Regional Authority implemented a series of initiatives that targeted this group, including business visits, regional events, research scholarships and grants for startups. Given the success of the project, it was renewed, and it received additional funding.

4.4. Create repatriation grants and fellowships

10. Creating and promoting opportunities through grants and fellowships targeting high-skilled individuals to move to their regions.	
Target	Sending Member States and regions
Leading Actor	Sending Member States and regions CERN

4.4.1. Making the Case

Pull factors, such as better job opportunities, play an important role in a person's decision to leave its home region. The evidence suggests that the same factors also affect the return decisions of these individuals: the probability of finding the right job opportunities, starting their own business, and the presence of good universities and research centres influence return decisions.³² This indicates that providing opportunities that target persons who worked on CERN projects can increase the chances of attracting them back.

4.4.2. Case of Success

BEWARE (Wallonia, Belgium)

To attract researchers to the Wallonia-Brussels Federation, the Department of Research Programmes of Wallonia created two funding programmes: the BEWARE Fellowship Industry and the BEWARE Fellowships Academia.³³ The first one was for Walloon SMEs to benefit from the expertise of researchers to encourage innovation. The second scheme allowed researchers to benefit from a stay at a university in the region. These programmes attracted not only foreign researchers but also those from the region that previously moved abroad. Some researchers decided to stay in the region after the end of the programmes.³³

4.5.Create repatriation incentives

11. Provide repatriation incentives for individuals who stayed at CERN to return to their home region.	
Target	Sending Member States/Regions
Leading Actor	Sending Member States and key regions CERN

4.5.1. Making the Case

Preferential tax schemes for highly skilled workers who live abroad are increasingly common in European countries. Monetary rewards can play an important factor, in location decisions. Evidence from schemes in the Netherlands and Denmark shows that tax incentives doubled the number of high-skilled migrants.^{34,35} A more recent study on an Italian programme, discussed below, that specifically targeted high-skilled Italians who had moved abroad found that eligible individuals were 27% more likely to move back.³⁶

As previously discussed, such schemes do not need to remain limited to direct financial incentives. The incentives can also be indirect such as installation and repatriation grants, dedicated job opportunities in government agencies, researcher and teaching positions in universities and scientific research opportunities in national leading research facilities.

4.5.2. Case of Success

Controesodo (Italy)

In 2010, Italy implemented a favourable tax policy (*Controesodo*) aimed at attracting high-skilled workers back to Italy. This policy provided a substantial income tax exemption for returning expatriates who had earned a college degree and were born in or after 1969.³⁶ In 2019, the eligibility was expanded, and the taxable share was lowered to 30% and made even more generous (10% for the first five years) to those who moved to southern regions.³⁶

4.6.Engage CERN staff and alumni abroad

12. Engaging CERN staff and alumni abroad through knowledge exchange and entrepreneurship programmes, mentorship schemes and awards.

Target	Sending Member States/Regions
Leading Actor	Sending Member States and key regions CERN

4.6.1. Making the Case

Migration of highly skilled persons is increasingly becoming a temporary phenomenon. These talented individuals often have international careers and move multiple times in their lives for learning and career opportunities.³² Even if they do not permanently return, they can maintain ties with their home country, serving as middlemen, linking businesses, universities and research centres in distant regions.³⁷ The movement of these workers is not necessarily a zero-sum game: with brain circulation, both sides can benefit.

4.6.2. Case of Success

SOMOPRO (Moravia, Czechia)

SOMOPRO is a grant scheme that was designed to facilitate brain circulation. Its aim was to attract researchers from abroad and from the rest of Czechia to the region. It also supported researchers who previously worked in the region to return.³³ The programme provided fellowships from 1 to 3 years to top foreign researchers or scientists who want to go back to the region after their experience abroad. The programme attracted researchers from 27 countries, almost half of the fellows that were attracted under SOMOPRO, remained in the region.

5. Spreading the Benefits of Tourism

5.1. Diagnosis

CERN is not only a prime destination for researchers from across the globe but also a major attraction for tourists. Until 2019, CERN welcomed about 150 000 visitors each year.¹ With the opening of the new visitor centre, Science Gateway, in 2023, first evidence from 2024 shows that this number is likely to more than double. CERN has recently been added to the Time Magazine World's Greatest Places to visit, which will most likely have a further effect on tourism inflow¹.

CERN visitors generate significant economic benefits including higher sustained demand for local services that contribute to the creation of jobs in retail and hospitality. These tangible direct economic and job creation benefits have been diligently analysed and documented.³⁸ By nature, these benefits tend to be spatially concentrated in the Geneva area and the neighbouring French municipalities where CERN is located. With an FCC project there is an opportunity to further expand the benefits to the Haute-Savoie department and at least four municipalities with experimental sites have expressed interest in such a development.

Several factors can explain this.

First, CERN's location in the vicinity of other tourist attractions limits the spatial spread of tourism benefits. Given Switzerland's high hospitality costs, visitors tend to allocate a significant part of their budget to the CERN experience and to nearby tourist attractions in France and Switzerland. The visit in the region lasts on average 4 days.³⁸

Second, many CERN visitors travel to the region because of their interest in CERN and to learn about the research first. Additional activities are, according to the surveys carried out over the last years, the second priority.³⁸ This explains also the fact that most visitors travel to CERN as part of a group. The motivation is the interest in science and technology and the itinerary focuses on CERN facilities and experiments, at most also further nearby scientific and cultural attractions (e.g. Roman excavations, United Nations, Mont Blanc, Lake Geneva, different museums).

Finally, there is still a lack of promotion regarding other attractions that could interest the CERN visitors. This includes, but is not limited to sport activities, hiking, natural reservations, further cities such as Evian, Annecy, Lyon, Dijon, Lausanne, Montreux, Fribourg, Bern, Luzern and more).

Our recommendations focus on this last factor and, more specifically, on making CERN **a more general gateway for science tourism**. This initiative revolves around promoting science tourism packages that include visits to other scientific attractions across Europe to help spreading the benefits also to other contributing countries.

¹ World's Greatest Places 2024, <https://time.com/6992395/cern-science-gateway/>, Time online.

5.2. Benefits for Member States and CERN

The increased influx of tourists can lead to higher tourism revenue for member states and stimulate job creation throughout the whole tourism supply chain. There are also additional benefits for CERN. By promoting other scientific destinations alongside its own offerings, CERN can enhance its appeal as a travel destination. The association with a broader range of scientific attractions can reinforce CERN's image as a leader in science and innovation.

5.3. Develop tour packages that include further destinations

13. Developing, together with tourism boards, local governments and other research facilities, science tour packages that feature additional scientific attractions across Europe and technology hubs in combination with other activities.

Target	Regions that do not currently benefit from CERN tourism benefits
Leading Actor	CERN Local actors Tourism boards Other European research facilities

5.3.1. Making the Case

By linking renowned scientific attractions with emerging scientific cities, such as winners of the European Capital of Innovation³⁹ and the European Rising Innovative City awards, these packages can direct tourist flows to under-visited areas, stimulating local demand in hospitality, retail, and transport services. Tailored packages could be developed for specific demographics and markets. This includes for instance combined physics and astronomy tours with CERN to visit the Gran Sasso laboratory in Italy, ITER in France, ESRF in Grenoble, MedAustron in Austria, CNAO and INFN in Italy, ESS in Sweden, ESO in Germany, ELI in Czechia and Hungary, and potentially many more. Other interesting destinations cover cultural and historic heritage sites in an enlarged perimeter of up to 600 km, reaching out to the neighbouring French, Italian, Austrian and German regions. The exploitation of train connections can play a role in the planning of those circuits.

5.3.2. Case of Success

VisitBritain's GREAT Gateway Innovation Fund (UK)

The Gateway Innovation Fund aims to provide financial assistance by way of a cash grant to a UK-registered Destination Management Organisation (DMO), UK-based tourism supplier or transport carrier to deliver international marketing activity for a specific inbound gateway or region.⁴⁰ The main goal is to encourage visitors to broaden their itineraries, boost visits across Britain, and support more destinations and local economies. It also incentivises destinations to create partnerships with businesses to boost the marketing activity.

6. Systematic Data Gathering for Science Policies

6.1. Diagnosis

While there is substantial evidence of CERN's socio-economic benefits through various pathways, there remain gaps in our understanding of what causes these effects and how they can be tuned. For example, what type of procurement contracts work best in terms of efficiency and social return? What type of unbundling of large contracts increases the participation of SMEs while keeping the process competitive?

To answer these questions, in view of an FCC project, **CERN should systematically and rigorously evaluate its investments and their impacts over sustained periods of time using robust methods.** There are several factors that make the pursuit of this objective challenging.

The first one is related to resources needed for the task. Currently, sufficient resources for conducting thorough studies over sustained periods of time are not allocated.

Second, evaluation and design for socio-economic return requires data gathered and managed centrally by the organisation. Today, this is not the case.

Finally, there is the issue of timing. Starting evaluations from the earliest phase can allow a more systematic collection of the necessary data, a better definition of the outcomes, and the possibility of developing robust evaluation methodologies, such as randomised control trials.

We recommend therefore the integration of robust evaluation throughout the entire FCC project. This includes allocating adequate resources to this task and sharing the data to allow economists to contribute to the evidence base.

6.2. Benefits for Member States and CERN

Gathering more solid evidence on the socio-economic effects of this scientific endeavour will benefit both the Member States and CERN. For Member States, a deeper understanding of what strategies are most effective in maximizing the socio-economic benefits of such large-scale scientific endeavours is crucial. Understanding what works can enhance the cost-effectiveness of the investments.

For CERN, these improvements in understanding and cost-effectiveness not only bolster the project's sustainability but also enhance its standing in the global scientific community. By leading in these areas, CERN can enlarge its leadership in science policy, demonstrating how cutting-edge research can be aligned with sound economic strategies and policy-making, positioning CERN as a model for integrating scientific innovation with socio-economic development and gaining further public support.

6.3. Establish a funding stream for socio-economic impact evaluation

14. Establishing a funding stream for sustained socio-economic impact evaluation and data collection from the outset of the FCC project.	
Target	All Member States
Leading Actor	CERN Other Research Infrastructures (optional)

6.3.1. Making the Case

Evidence of the socio-economic benefits that CERN can generate exists, but there is still a lack of understanding of what works best to maximise these socio-economic effects. Drawing from the success of international development, such as the J-PAL (Jameel Poverty Action Lab) research centre, where rigorous field experiments have improved the effectiveness of policies, a similar approach could be adopted for the FCC.⁴¹

Assessment requires resources, but investment in such initiatives has lagged.⁴² To continue to build evidence of what works, CERN, together with its partners, should establish a dedicated funding stream for data collection and analysis, policy development and evaluation. Starting early allows for a more systematic collection of the necessary data, a better definition of the outcomes and more robust methodologies.⁴³ In addition, embedding evaluation from the start can offer early insights into what works and how to improve cost-effectiveness. Given its duration, this is even more relevant for the FCC.

This funding stream can be set up in collaboration with other Research Infrastructures and partners (e.g. ERICs, EIROForum members, ESFRI listed RIs, ESA, LDG members), thus leveraging the investments in the data collection, using the same methodologies and transferring the lessons learnt.

When designing the evaluation programme, CERN can continue to rely on external expertise (e.g. economics experts that it has engaged with in the past) while expanding and developing internal capabilities through training by the external experts. By building more evidence on what works, CERN could reinforce its role as a leader not just in science but also in science policy.

6.3.2. Cases of Success

What Works Centres Network (UK)

Launched in 2013, the network comprises 10 independent research centres with the aim of embedding robust evidence at the heart of local and national policymaking and covering more than £200 billion of public expenditure in areas such as crime, education, local growth and early intervention.⁴⁴ The What Works Centres systematically assess and synthesise the evidence base on different areas and issue guidance to decision-makers. Where evidence is weak or unavailable, they seek to fill such gaps by commissioning new research or encouraging organisations to do so. The centres also train practitioners on how to use the evidence and how to conduct their evaluations.

NSF's Directorate for Technology, Innovation and Partnerships (TIP) (US)

TIP is a cross-cutting platform that integrates the existing directorates with the mission of advancing the societal impact of the NSF. TIP runs a series of pilots that it views as experiments that can provide the opportunity to learn something new or improve the NSF approach to funding science.⁴⁵ These pilots begin by developing a hypothesis, testing it and evaluating the outcomes before deciding on further funding and scaling. These pilots are run in partnership with other universities, research centres and businesses.

6.4. Operate an Open Data portal for socio-economic impact data

15. Operate an Open Data portal that attracts social scientists to use CERN to continue to evaluate the socio-economic impact of investment in science.

Target	All Member States
Leading Actor	CERN Other Research Infrastructures (optional)

6.4.1. Making the Case

Given the existing gaps in the knowledge on the socio-economic effects of science funding, there is a compelling case for CERN to develop and operate an open data portal for social scientists. This portal would provide structured access to CERN data and data of the partners that team up with CERN on socio-economic impact studies.

Examples of such data include but are not limited to information to estimate the effects on salary premium for ECRs, tourism statistics, industrial multipliers, the value of science products, survival data on spinoff companies, data for the estimation of socio-economic impacts, environmental externalities and benefits and other relevant databases.

This data portal would allow the social sciences community to evaluate the effects of science funding, significantly reducing the need for CERN to utilize its own internal capabilities or funding.

By gaining new insights into the impact of investing in fundamental research, CERN can improve transparency and accountability to its funders. CERN could work with organisations like the Open Data Institute, which helps public authorities share their data and develop their data infrastructures.

6.4.2. Case of Success

Kohesio (Europe)

Launched in 2022 by the European Commission, to improve transparency and increase awareness of EU investments, Kohesio is a public online platform gathering all the information on more than 1.5 million projects in EU countries, funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the Cohesion Fund and the European Social Fund (ESF).⁴⁶ The platform provides details about funding and beneficiaries of each project and the data is available in all 27 languages. This allows citizens, journalists, researchers and policymakers to access comprehensive data on EU-funded projects.

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